

RESULTS OF PROPERTIES OF FIBONACCI NUMBERS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the properties of Fibonacci numbers with proofs. In addition, some resulting properties are derived from the properties of Fibonacci numbers. The article can be used by students of higher educational institutions and those preparing for the Olympiad in mathematics.

Keywords: *Fibonacci numbers, recurrence relation, golden ratio, major ratio, minor ratio.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known that $u_n = u_{n-1} + u_{n-2}$ ($n \geq 3$) with $u_1 = u_2 = 1$, the sequence determined by means of recurrent equality is called Fibonacci series, and its terms are called Fibonacci numbers. The phrase Fibonacci numbers can be found in the nineteenth-century works devoted to interesting mathematics by Eduard Lucca. Fibonacci (this word is shortened from the Italian words "filius Bonacci", which means the son of Bonacci) is the nickname of Leonardo Pisanoski, who lived in the city of Pisa in Italy in the 12th and 13th centuries. Bonacci was engaged in trade in Italy and Algeria. Leonardo received his primary education in Algeria. He had learned the Indian positional decimal system and zero from his Arabic teachers.

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_n(u_n + u_{n+1}) &= u_{n+1}(u_n + u_{n-1}) + (-1)^{n+1} \\
 u_n u_{n+2} &= u_{n+1}^2 + (-1)^{n+1} \\
 u_{n+1}^2 &= u_n u_{n+2} + (-1)^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

Property 7. $u_1 u_2 + u_2 u_3 + u_3 u_4 + \dots + u_{2n-1} u_{2n} = u_{2n}^2$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &u_2(u_1 + u_3) + u_4(u_3 + u_5) + \dots + u_{2n-1}(u_{2n-2} + u_{2n}) = \\
 &= (u_3 - u_1)(u_1 + u_3) + (u_5 - u_3)(u_3 + u_5) + \dots \\
 &\dots + (u_{2n} - u_{2n-2})(u_{2n} + u_{2n-2}) = u_3^2 - u_1^2 + u_5^2 - u_3^2 + u_7^2 - u_5^2 + \\
 &+ \dots + u_{2n}^2 - u_{2n-2}^2 = u_{2n}^2
 \end{aligned}$$

Property 8. $u_1 u_2 + u_2 u_3 + u_3 u_4 + \dots + u_{2n} u_{2n+1} = u_{2n+1}^2 - 1$

Property 9. $nu_1 + (n-1)u_2 + (n-2)u_3 + \dots + 2u_{n-1} + u_n =$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (u_1 + u_2 + u_3 + \dots + u_n) + (u_1 + u_2 + u_3 + \dots + u_{n-1}) + (u_1 + u_2 + u_3 + \\
 &+ \dots + u_{n-2}) + \dots + u_1 = u_{n+2} - 1 + u_{n+1} - 1 + u_n - 1 + u_{n-1} - 1 + u_1 = \\
 &= u_{n+4} - (n+3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Property 10.

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_1 + 2u_2 + 3u_3 + \dots + nu_n &= (n+1)(u_1 + u_2 + u_3 + \dots + u_n) - \\
 (nu_1 + (n-1)u_2 + (n-2)u_3 + \dots + 2u_{n-1} + u_n) &= \\
 = (n+1)(u_{n+2} - 1) - (u_{n+4} - (n+3)) &= nu_{n+2} - u_{n-3} + 2
 \end{aligned}$$

Property 11. $u_n = \sum_{k=1}^n C_{n-k-1}^k$

Property 12. $u_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \left[\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^n - \left(\frac{1-\sqrt{5}}{2} \right)^n \right]. [1]$

RESULTS

$$u_{n+2}^2 - u_{n+1}^2 = u_n u_{n+3}$$

Because

$$u_{n+2}^2 - u_{n+1}^2 = (u_{n+2} - u_{n+1})(u_{n+2} + u_{n+1}) = u_n u_{n+3}.$$

Likewise

$$u_{n+m} = u_{n-1} u_m + u_n u_{m+1}$$

From this

$$u_{n+m} = u_{n+1} u_{m+1} + u_{n-1} u_{m-1}$$

CONCLUSION

It can be seen that Fibonacci numbers have an incomparable role in the solution of many natural and life problems. In addition, Fibonacci numbers are also related to the golden section. The golden section of a given section is defined as dividing it into two such parts. here, the ratio of the length of the entire section to the length of the large part and the ratio of the length of the large part to the length of the small part are mutually equal. It is not difficult to determine that the value of this ratio is equal to α_1 . The interesting thing is that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{u_{n+1}}{u_n} = \alpha_1$$

will be.

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